

Supplementary Material

Tooth Extraction versus Endodontic Treatment: Impacts on Systemic Inflammatory Biomarkers – A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis

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Table S1. Data extraction sheet with study characteristics and biomarker values

Author/Year	Biomarker	Group/Intervention	n	Baseline (Mean ± SD)	2w/3m (Mean ± SD)	6m (Mean ± SD)	12m (Mean ± SD)	24m (Mean ± SD)	Notes
Agrawal 2022	IL-6	Single sitting RCT	150	156 ± 11.05	-	45.01 ± 21.04	-	-	Pre vs 1w
Agrawal 2022	IL-6	Multiple sitting RCT	150	143 ± 10.21	-	29.56 ± 12.01	-	-	Pre vs 1w
Agrawal 2022	TNF- α	Single sitting RCT	150	6.12 ± 1.23	-	5.10 ± 0.21	-	-	Pre vs 1w
Agrawal 2022	TNF- α	Multiple sitting RCT	150	5.97 ± 1.00	-	3.12 ± 0.91	-	-	Pre vs 1w
Agrawal 2022	hs-CRP	Single sitting RCT	150	2.13 ± 0.20	-	1.56 ± 0.11	-	-	Pre vs 1w
Agrawal 2022	hs-CRP	Multiple sitting RCT	150	2.01 ± 0.01	-	1.12 ± 0.01	-	-	Pre vs 1w
Palafox- Sánchez 2023	IL-6	AAA	46	[~17.7 ± 16.3]	46	~17.7	~16.3	-	Estimated from boxplot
Palafox- Sánchez 2023	IL-6	Controls	32	[~6.0 ± 3.0]	32	~6.0	~3.0	-	Estimated from boxplot
Palafox- Sánchez 2023	TNF- α	AAA	46	[~6.7 ± 4.4]	46	~6.7	~4.4	-	Estimated from boxplot
Palafox- Sánchez 2023	TNF- α	Controls	32	[~3.0 ± 1.5]	32	~3.0	~1.5	-	Estimated from boxplot
Palafox- Sánchez 2023	IL-10	AAA	46	[~6.0 ± 1.5]	46	~6.0	~1.5	-	Estimated from boxplot
Palafox- Sánchez 2023	IL-10	Controls	32	[~5.5 ± 0.7]	32	~5.5	~0.7	-	Estimated from boxplot
Georgiou 2023	IL-6	AP patients	27	-0.04	27	SE≈0.1 4	-	-	See Appendix Table A1
Georgiou 2023	TNF- α	AP patients	27	-0.18	27	SE≈0.1 0	-	-	LMM Δ -0.20 at Visit 3
Georgiou 2023	CRP	AP patients	27	- 1313800	27	SE≈77 8000	-	-	Trend not significant
Wang 2023	CRP	G1	65	2.3 ± 2.6	1.5 ± 1.9 (2w)	2.2 ± 1.9	-	-	↓ baseline to 2w
Wang 2023	CRP	G2	82	1.8 ± 2.1	1.2 ± 1.4 (2w)	2.1 ± 1.0	-	-	↓ baseline to 2w/3m
Wang 2023	CRP	G3	76	1.4 ± 2.3	0.9 ± 1.8 (2w)	1.6 ± 0.8	-	-	↓ baseline to 2w/6m
Wang 2023	IL-6	G1	65	101.0 ± 39.8	79.3 ± 35.1 (2w)	80.8 ± 37.6	-	-	↓ at all FU
Wang 2023	IL-6	G2	82	97.6 ± 31.9	79.3 ± 26.9 (2w)	80.8 ± 30.2	-	-	↓ at all FU

Wang 2023	IL-6	G3	76	81.6 ± 28.9	72.4 ± 26.8 (2w)	75.6 ± 31.2	-	-	↓ at all FU
Wang 2023	TNF- α	G1	65	1163 ± 153	924 ± 97 (2w)	717 ± 128	-	-	↓ strong
Wang 2023	TNF- α	G2	82	1126 ± 185	876 ± 156 (2w)	679 ± 134	-	-	↓ strong
Wang 2023	TNF- α	G3	76	1199 ± 159	950 ± 104 (2w)	712 ± 134	-	-	↓ strong
Bakhsh 2022	IL-6	Re-RCT	35	50	5.75	2.40	-	-	Median (IQR) – convert
Bakhsh 2022	IL-6	Surgery	30	65	7.06	7.93	-	-	Median (IQR) – convert
Bakhsh 2022	TNF- α	Re-RCT	35	50	12.44	4.14	-	-	Median (IQR) – convert
Bakhsh 2022	TNF- α	Surgery	30	65	18.37	22.66	-	-	Median (IQR) – convert
Bakhsh 2022	hs-CRP	Re-RCT	35	50	31141.7 2	29060. 64	-	-	Median (IQR) – convert
Bakhsh 2022	hs-CRP	Surgery	30	65	78287.5 6	87056. 44	-	-	Median (IQR) – convert

IL-6, interleukin-6; TNF- α , tumor necrosis factor alpha; IL-10, interleukin-10; CRP, C-reactive protein; hs-CRP, high-sensitivity C-reactive protein; RCT, randomized controlled trial; Re-RCT, retreatment randomized controlled trial; AP, apical periodontitis; AAA, acute apical abscess; G1/G2/G3, intervention groups; n, sample size; Mean \pm SD, mean \pm standard deviation; IQR, interquartile range; SE, standard error; FU, follow-up; LMM Δ , linear mixed model – delta; Pre vs 1w, baseline compared with one week; 2w/3m/6m/12m/24m, 2 weeks, 3 months, 6 months, 12 months, 24 months.

Table S2. Risk of bias assessments of included studies

Reference	Study design	Tool used	Risk of bias judgment	Main sources of bias
Agrawal et al., 2022	Comparative observational (quasi-experimental)	NOS	Moderate risk	Selection bias (non-random allocation), lack of blinding, short follow-up (1 week).
Palafox-Sánchez et al., 2023	Prospective longitudinal (observational)	NOS	Low risk	Adequate control group and follow-up; main limitation was small sample size.
Bakhsh et al., 2022	Prospective clinical study	NOS	Moderate risk	Some loss to follow-up, outcome measures partly reported as medians (possible selective reporting).
Georgiou et al., 2023	Prospective case-control	NOS	Moderate risk	Small sample (n=53), biomarker values partly below detection limit, potential confounders (age-related interactions).
Wang et al., 2023	Prospective observational (diabetic patients with AP)	NOS	Low risk	Large sample (n=223), clear outcome reporting; limitation: single-center design.

RCT, root canal treatment; re-RCT, root canal retreatment; AP, apical periodontitis; AAA, acute apical abscess; CRP, C-reactive protein; hs-CRP, high-sensitivity C-reactive protein; IL, interleukin; IL-6, interleukin-6; IL-10, interleukin-10; TNF- α , tumor necrosis factor-alpha; T2D, type 2 diabetes mellitus; wk, week(s); d, day(s); mo, month(s).

Figure S1. PRISMA 2020 flow diagram of study selection

